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Methods of Enhancing Foreign Language Education for Students with Special Educational Needs in HEIs

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***Abstract.** The purpose of this article is to investigate and propose ways to improve foreign language teaching for students with special educational needs in higher educational institutions. The task of the article is to analyze modern*

*challenges, develop adaptive learning strategies and research technical and didactic support. It aims to create a structure that supports an inclusive, adaptive and supportive learning environment for students with special educational needs learning foreign languages, taking into account both academic and social aspects. The authors used general scientific **methods** of analysis, synthesis, deduction and induction. The **results** of the study showed that the choice of effective teaching methods to increase the academic potential of students with special educational needs during foreign language learning in higher educational institutions is determined by various forms of work. Interest in learning a foreign language is increased by interactive technologies that enable different categories of students to participate in active foreign language communication and, accordingly, develop the ability of students with special educational needs to cooperate with others. Information and communication technologies allow not only to compensate and correct the consequences of health disorders of such students in a multimedia foreign language environment, but also to activate cognitive activity taking into account their individual educational needs. So, as a **conclusion**, education, upbringing and development of students with special needs should be carried out according to individual plans and programs, and the personality of the teacher plays an important role in inclusive education. Inclusive education in the conditions of war in Ukraine requires a comprehensive approach that takes into account physical, psychological and educational needs. This requires efforts from both the state and society as a whole to ensure the future of young people, regardless of their origin and state of health.*

Keywords: *inclusive educational environment, adapted educational programs, extracurricular activities, didactic materials, health-saving technologies, interactive technologies, inclusive technologies.*

Шляхи вдосконалення іноземної мовної освіти для студентів з особливими освітніми потребами у ЗВО

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Анотація.** Мета цієї статті – дослідити та запропонувати шляхи вдосконалення викладання іноземної мови для студентів з особливими освітніми потребами у вищих навчальних закладах. Завдання статті – проаналізувати сучасні виклики, розробити стратегії адаптивного навчання та дослідити технічну та дидактичну підтримку. Вона спрямована на створення структури, яка підтримує інклюзивне, адаптивне та підтримуюче навчальне середовище для студентів з особливими освітніми потребами, що вивчають іноземні мови, беручи до уваги як академічні, так і соціальні аспекти. Автори використовували загально-наукові **методи

аналізу, синтезу, дедукції та індукції. **Результати** дослідження показали, що вибір ефективних методів навчання для підвищення академічного потенціалу студентів з особливими освітніми потребами під час вивчення іноземної мови у вищих навчальних закладах визначається різноманітними формами роботи. Інтерес до вивчення іноземної мови підвищують інтерактивні технології, які дають можливість різним категоріям студентів брати участь в активному іномовному спілкуванні і, відповідно, розвивають здатність студентів з особливими освітніми потребами до співпраці з іншими. Інформаційно-комунікаційні технології дозволяють не тільки компенсувати та коригувати наслідки порушень здоров'я таких студентів у мультимедійному іномовному середовищі, а й активізувати пізнавальну діяльність з урахуванням їхніх індивідуальних освітніх потреб. Отже, як **висновок**, навчання, виховання та розвиток учнів з особливими потребами має здійснюватися за індивідуальними планами та програмами, а особистість вчителя відіграє важливу роль в інклюзивній освіті. Інклюзивна освіта в умовах війни в Україні потребує комплексного підходу, який враховує фізичні, психологічні та освітні потреби. Це вимагає зусиль як з боку держави, так і суспільства в цілому для забезпечення майбутнього молодих людей, незалежно від їхнього походження та стану здоров'я.

Ключові слова: інклюзивне освітнє середовище, адаптовані освітні програми, позааудиторна робота, дидактичні матеріали, здоров'язберігаючі технології, інтерактивні технології, інклюзивні технології.

A general statement of the problem and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks (Introduction). In the context of modern globalization, the job market requires professionals who speak foreign languages. This skill opens the way to quality higher education and successful employment.

This requirement is relevant for all students, including those with disabilities and health conditions, as ensuring equal access to quality education for young people in accordance with their interests and aptitudes meets the needs of modern society in terms of professional training. Learning foreign languages helps to overcome psychological barriers to communication, to master the culture of other countries, to read professional literature without translation, to participate in international conferences and internships, and to increase the chances of getting a well-paid job and building a successful career.

It is worth noting that meeting the educational needs of students with disabilities and health disadvantages requires intellectual and psychological mobilization, which is provided by a tolerant social environment in an inclusive university where students, teachers, and administration cooperate. Joint activities in special educational facilities contribute to the socialization of individuals, to the self-realization of this group and to the formation of equal partnerships with other social groups [1].

With the development of inclusive education and the emergence of relevant state documents regulating this type of education, the issue of creating effective methods of teaching people with disabilities in higher education arises. The concept of inclusive education in Ukraine is particularly relevant in the context of military conflict. War creates numerous challenges, such as physical and psychological trauma, forced displacement, disruption of family ties, and other social problems that require an adaptive approach to education. The war in Ukraine has led to an increase in the number of children and young people with special educational needs, both as a direct result of the conflict (trauma, stress) and as a result of changes in the socio-economic environment. A significant number of internally displaced persons (IDPs) have to adjust to new communities, which requires the development of special support programs. Children who have

experienced traumatic events need special psychological support, which should be integrated into the educational process. The goals and objectives of modern inclusive education dictate the need for a continuous creative search for teachers and the justified implementation of effective educational technologies in teaching, including foreign languages, for the successful socialization of everyone, especially those affected by military aggression. The problem of teaching a foreign language in an inclusive educational environment has become a central topic of numerous scientific discussions, although it was previously considered inappropriate. The use of inclusive technologies in foreign language teaching is currently insufficiently studied and needs to be elaborated in more detail, taking into account modern educational standards.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In recent years, the problem of adaptation of people with disabilities to life in modern society has become particularly relevant and acute, arousing justified scientific interest. This issue has been the focus of research by such scholars as N. Stelmah [3], O. Omelchuk [3], A. Boichuk [3], O. Kazachiner [5], A. Kapska [6], N. Matveyeva [7], Yu. Shcherbiak [8], S. Susanto [9], D. Nanda [9] M. Calego [10], C. Busch [10], V. Kirvas [11], H. Vasianovych [12], T. Blyzniuk [12], O. Budnyk [12, 13], B. Kassie Shifere [18] and others.

At the same time, modern pedagogical science is actively engaged in education reform, especially in the field of dissemination and implementation of integration ideas. The peculiarities, aspects and problems of reforming national education are highlighted in the works of such scholars as H. Tymoshko [2], V. Hladush [2], S. Sydoriv [4], L. Slyvka [14], H. Sivkovzch [14], O. Budnyk [14, 17], O. Tytun [14], A. Boichuk [14], O. Taranchenko [15], M. Shved [16], M. Kotyk [17] and others.

In addition to the scholars mentioned above, theorists and practitioners at home and abroad are actively engaged in the inclusive education issues.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. This study highlights the importance of inclusive practices in language education, given both the unique cognitive and social challenges these students face and the impact of the socio-political context in Ukraine, including the recent military conflict. The study examines different teaching methods, adaptive technologies, and support systems tailored to the specific needs of students with disabilities in order to foster an inclusive educational environment that promotes equal access to professional and academic opportunities.

Formulation of the objectives of the article. The **purpose** of this article is to investigate and propose ways to improve foreign language education for students with special educational needs in higher education institutions (HEIs). This approach is designed to support students' socialization, cognitive development, and language acquisition, ultimately contributing to their successful integration in both academic and professional settings.

The **objectives** of this article include: analysis of current challenges, development of adaptive learning strategies, study of technological and didactic support, formulation of recommendations for teacher training. These tasks jointly aim to create a structure that supports an inclusive, adaptive and supportive learning environment for foreign language students with special educational needs, taking into account both academic and social aspects.

Presentation of the main material of the study with a full justification of the obtained scientific results (Results of the study). Special educational needs of people with disabilities are often perceived by society as an obstacle to mastering a foreign language. Limitations in the ability to hear, write, lack of ability to quickly master educational and work skills require appropriate

methodological and didactic tools in accordance with the individual educational needs of students. Despite the prevailing opinion about the complexity of learning a foreign language by students with special educational needs, associated with limitations in mastering types of speech activity in their native language, their interest in a foreign language is growing. Interest is determined by intellectual, professional and personal development and is associated with the possibilities of their socialization in the framework of cooperation and communication for subsequent employment. In this regard, in the theory and practice of foreign language education at a university, it is important to update the ways of improving the professionally oriented training of these students.

According to the last research [2], the main problems hindering the process of integration of people with special educational needs into higher education institutions (HEIs) are:

- insufficient number of specialists to work with students with special educational needs; lack of training of specialists such as psychologists, rehabilitation therapists, social workers to work with this category of youth in the education system;
- the timeframe for studying for people with special educational needs in secondary and higher education institutions according to the state standard does not allow them to acquire the necessary level of knowledge;
- lack of a system of retraining and further training of teachers in higher education institutions to teach students with special educational needs;
- inadequate consideration of medical experience for health professionals working in higher education institutions;
- insufficient material and technical support of higher education institutions;
- limited funding for medical, social and psychological support of the educational process of persons with disabilities;

- lack of a regulatory and legislative framework for the education of persons with disabilities in higher education institutions;

- lack of cooperation between the Ministry of Education, Health, Labor and Social Policy, and the State Committee for Family and Youth Affairs in matters of education and rehabilitation of persons with disabilities due to different sources of funding.

It should be noted that there are many problems that students face. According to our observations in the process of teaching at the faculties of Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, the main ones are: difficulties in perceiving the educational material, lack of confidence in their abilities, impaired concentration and disabilities that interfere with the perception of the material.

The problem of working with students with special needs during distance learning is particularly acute. In general, no one knows for sure whether inclusion and distance learning can coexist in the long term. Online learning causes significant limitations in social life, including communication with peers, walking, and common interests, which leads to problems in identifying with the group and problems of recognition [3].

Thus, there are three forms of student adaptation to the conditions of study in higher education institutions (HEIs):

Formal adaptation - cognitive and informational adaptation of students to the new environment, structure, requirements and obligations of studying at a higher education institution.

Socio-psychological (social) adaptation is the process of internal integration of groups of first-year students and the integration of these groups with the student environment as a whole.

Didactic adaptation is the preparation of students for new forms and methods of teaching in higher education.

Regarding the assessment system, the problem of assessing the knowledge of students with disabilities has undergone significant reform and has become more objective. Previously, there was an informal tradition of awarding higher grades to students with disabilities "with sympathy." However, now that students feel like equal members of the educational process, this need and tradition have disappeared. Students with disabilities consciously refuse any privileges during the assessment process. Most of them demonstrate even higher knowledge than their non-disabled peers.

In the world practice, there is a noticeable shift from a culture of utility to a culture of dignity. Within the framework of this person-centered concept, a person with congenital or acquired disabilities, regardless of their capacity and usefulness to society, is considered an object of special social assistance and care. This is aimed at creating conditions for the fullest possible self-realization of their personality and the realization of all opportunities for integration into society [4].

Psychological and pedagogical support in higher education institutions is typical for both students with disabilities and other young people. Pedagogical support aims to optimize the teaching of educational material to students with disabilities in the most receptive form for them, the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies, the provision of teaching materials, etc. Psychological support is aimed at strengthening and preserving the psychological health of the student, providing the necessary assistance for adaptation to the integrated educational environment [5]. Empathy is important on the part of the teacher, who, building communication, treats the problems and needs of the student with care and understanding, contributing to his or her personal development.

According to A. Kapska, psychological and pedagogical support involves both integrated and special and differentiated methods of teaching and upbringing, resulting in the activity and value alignment of the study group. At the same time,

appropriate communication between a teacher and young people should be spontaneous, open and personal [6].

Thus, psychological and pedagogical support for students with disabilities should be based on the hierarchy of student needs. This includes the organization of the environment, the need for communication, access to information, inclusion in social processes and adequate self-identification.

Didactic support for foreign language teaching is based on the use of visuals and didactic materials, taking into account the diverse educational needs of university students. This contributes to a better perception of information related to their future professional activities. In this context, the compensatory means represented by audiovisual learning tools provide visibility and stimulate student work.

Learning in joint study groups of 7-15 people, where all students are assessed on equal terms, is based on adapted educational programs designed to take into account their developmental disabilities. When implementing these programs, university faculty should design an individual educational trajectory for such students, focusing on the specifics of their cognitive activity. The stages of designing this trajectory are setting an educational goal of individual development, diagnosing students, reflection, creating didactic support for students, specifying the goal and designing a route sheet [7]. Thus, individualization of the process of foreign language acquisition contributes to a more effective organization of vocationally oriented training in an inclusive university environment. This is a time-consuming task without understanding how best to combine organizational forms of foreign language teaching at the university and select didactic materials taking into account students' health disorders.

In the process of teaching students with special educational needs, it is not planned to reduce thematic sections, although the amount of lexical and

grammatical material needs to be significantly reduced due to its "low practical relevance and complexity" [8]. The emphasis should be on commonly used constructions used in professionally oriented foreign language communication. It is advisable to study familiar topics in a frontal manner, and involving students with special educational needs in active cognitive activities is possible through a multisensory approach.

A multisensory approach to teaching students different types of foreign language speech activities involves the use of visual, auditory and kinesthetic methods. These methods ensure teaching a foreign language in a logical sequence, regular practice and repeated repetition of what has been learned, as well as continuous interaction between students and the teacher [9], which contributes to modeling situations of professionally oriented foreign language communication.

It is important to involve students with special educational needs in extracurricular activities in the university environment where they receive vocational training. Such activities include joint listening to music and watching movies in a foreign language that reflect vocationally oriented situations, followed by a discussion of their content [10]; staging and staging plays in a foreign language in which vocationally oriented situations are played out. Educational games, known as quests, are also gaining popularity, allowing the use of the territory or information resources to solve a professionally oriented problem, implementing educational tasks according to a route determined in advance by the teacher.

Didactic materials for students with visual impairment.

The use of the speech experience of visually impaired students and specially designed didactic materials is aimed at involving them in the practice of foreign language speech activities. During classes, the teacher should comment on what is written on the blackboard and duplicate tables and diagrams in print. This

presentation of the material implies the teacher's ability to convey professionally oriented foreign language information to different categories of students. Students with visual impairments have special requirements for materials that must be presented in the form of an audio file, an electronic document, a printed document, including texts in Braille [11].

Didactic materials for students with hearing impairment.

For students with hearing impairment, the practice of foreign language speech activity is based on joint activities with all categories of students and the use of visual materials. It is important for students with special educational needs to sit so that they can see all participants in the discussion, as this is necessary for them to gain new social experience [12] and to perceive complex professional terms. The teacher should use handouts with explanations of lexical items and grammatical structures, as well as computer presentations [13].

Effective use of dictionaries to work on lexical and grammatical structures and control of their acquisition and use in foreign language speech allow students with hearing impairment to master various types of foreign language speech activities. Professionally oriented audio and video materials with subtitles will also be useful.

Didactic materials for students with musculoskeletal disorders.

Students with musculoskeletal disorders are characterized by an insufficient level of information perception, so the amount of material should be reduced and be visual. It is important to present the material in a structured way, illustrating the key terms necessary for professional-oriented foreign language communication. For this purpose, presentations (including those created by students themselves), videos, training films, video clips, excerpts from cartoons and feature films, various electronic applications and podcasts are used to help meet the special educational needs of students.

The insufficient level of information perception also affects the peculiarities of foreign language production due to students' speech defects. To improve the learning of lexical and grammatical structures, you can use the pronunciation of words and phrases in a chant, as well as songs. The predominance of group work and role-playing games contributes to the socialization of students with musculoskeletal disorders; preparing a multimedia presentation of a professionally oriented nature will be more effective in group work.

Health-saving technologies.

Health-saving technologies aimed at protecting and promoting the health of students with special educational needs are coming to the fore. These technologies are used not only in adaptive physical education and sports classes, but also in foreign language classes, where the teacher organizes physical activity breaks and offers special exercises. This helps to prevent overwork by maintaining a protective regimen during classes that discuss professionally-oriented topics. In this way, students gain experience in changing activities, which will be useful in the future [14].

Interactive technologies.

Interactive technologies are in the first place in the use of interactive technologies that allow engaging all categories of students in active foreign language communication and, accordingly, developing the ability of students with special educational needs to cooperate professionally with others [15]. Methods such as brainstorming, project method, case method, trainings, role-playing and business games, and portfolios are promising.

Brainstorming creates conditions for students to express their opinions on the proposed problem without fear of making mistakes [16]. This contributes to the development of foreign language writing and speaking skills, as well as the implementation of the project method, which allows students to engage in joint

activities to prepare and present a professionally oriented product of their activities in a foreign language. The project method is a tool for interaction in group work, when all categories of students learn to take responsibility for their work, which is an important skill for a specialist. The emphasis on joint activities is also present in the case method, when a situation of success is preceded by analysis and team decision-making. Both the project method and the case method imitate the process of solving professionally oriented tasks, so gaining such experience in a higher education institution allows students with special educational needs to prepare for working together with future colleagues.

The trainings allow students with special educational needs to experience professionally oriented foreign language communication (linguistic and non-linguistic) by interacting with different categories of students. Especially in the case of limited personal social experience, it is important for students to analyze the perception of themselves and others using foreign language tools. The interest in learning a foreign language is also reinforced by role-playing and business games, which activate cognitive activity through playing roles in life or professional situations. The roles of a speaker, expert or jury member, distributed among students with special educational needs, increase motivation to learn a foreign language through emotional "living" of the situation, manifestation of individual qualities and abilities of the personality, formation of communication skills.

Information and communication technologies.

Information and communication technologies allow not only to compensate and correct the consequences of students' developmental disorders in a multimedia foreign language environment, but also to intensify their cognitive activity taking into account individual educational needs. In particular, the integration of these technologies into the educational process of the university increases students'

motivation to learn a foreign language, creates conditions for the formation and development of students' communication skills and language skills [17].

To realize this, it is necessary to equip classrooms with multimedia equipment, which includes a multimedia projector, speakers, a computer, Internet access, as well as special software that provides adaptation of computer equipment management, data entry and presentation of multimedia information flows. This equipment enhances the ability of students with special educational needs to receive and process professionally oriented information with the help of screen magnifiers, cochlear implants, virtual keyboards, etc. using multimedia learning tools that provide visibility, informativeness, mobility and emotionality of the information presented.

In addition, students with locomotor disorders should have unimpeded access to classrooms that can be redesigned to meet their individual needs. Such equipment and space organization should be taken into account in future professional activities, as together they are a condition for the accessibility of foreign language communication.

It is effective to use a learning management system, for example, the university platform d-learn, whose educational environment facilitates the organization of interactive interaction by adapting the elements of a professionally oriented course to the individual educational needs of students and choosing the time of completion of tasks. A network form of organizing classes in the process of research is also advisable. Involvement of different educational organizations in this process provides additional practice of foreign language skills and abilities [18].

It should be borne in mind that a technical specialist is needed who can provide qualified support for the education of students with special educational needs, along with a tutor, psychologist, typhlopedagogue, sign language teacher,

sign language interpreter and social worker. Due to the difficulties in recruiting qualified staff, teachers often have to introduce information and communication technologies into the process of teaching professionally oriented foreign language communication on their own, so regular professional development is necessary.

Conclusions. The variety of forms of work determines the choice of effective educational technologies that enhance the academic potential of students with special educational needs while learning a foreign language in a higher education institution. The first place is occupied by health-saving technologies aimed at protecting and improving the health of these students. The interest in learning a foreign language is reinforced by interactive technologies that make it possible to engage different categories of students in active foreign language communication and, accordingly, to develop the ability of students with special educational needs to cooperate with others.

Information and communication technologies allow not only to compensate and correct the consequences of health disorders of these students in a multimedia foreign language environment, but also to activate their cognitive activity taking into account their individual educational needs.

As for foreign language teachers working with students with special needs, we believe that they should be trained to effectively apply specific forms, methods and techniques of teaching a foreign language to students with special educational needs. In addition, we should not forget about the use of new information technologies in teaching, non-verbal means of communication, visual, verbal and practical methods of teaching a foreign language, various types of didactic games (including speech games), non-traditional lessons, etc.

It is important to note that the education, upbringing and development of students with special needs should be based on individual plans and programs. The decisive role in an inclusive university is played by the personality of the teacher.

The problem for universities is that teachers of specialized disciplines usually do not have defectology and psychological training, and the technologies for teaching disciplines differ significantly according to the peculiarities of students' perception of educational material.

Therefore, an important key to the successful inclusion of students with disabilities is the special training of teachers to work in integrated groups. This involves familiarization with functional differences, peculiarities of development of students of different nosologies and their perception of educational material, methods of teaching them academic disciplines and the best international experience of inclusion of such students. To ensure the effective work of teachers in an inclusive environment, it is necessary to organize a permanent seminar to improve their skills.

Inclusive education in the context of war in Ukraine requires a comprehensive approach, taking into account physical, psychological and educational needs. This requires efforts not only from the state but also from the entire society to ensure a future for young people, regardless of their background or health status.

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